

**The Directive Effect of Substituents on the Cyclisation
of Substituted *s*-Diarylthiocarbamides. Part III.
The Effect of the Carbethoxy Group on the
Formation of Anilinobenzthiazoles
from *p*-Carbethoxy-*s*-Diphenyl-
thiocarbamides and Bromine.**

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It has been shown in the course of earlier investigations that the nitro and cyano groups in *p*-substituted-*s*-diphenylthiocarbamides do not direct thiazole cyclisation by bromine in the sense opposite to that of *o*:*p*-directive substituents, but give rise to anilinobenzthiazole derivatives in which the *meta*-directive substituent appears in the 1-arylamino grouping (Hunter and Jones, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 2190; Hunter, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 436). The *meta*-directive properties of these two groups have been attributed to the presence of the semipolar double bond in the former, the positive end of which tends to attract electrons from all parts of the molecule, and to the tendency of the system of the six electrons which are mutually shared between two atomic nuclei in the latter to attract additional electrons in order to obtain a more stable association of eight or ten electrons (Baker, Cooper and Ingold, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 426). It, therefore, appeared of interest to examine the effect of the carbethoxy group whose *meta*-directive tendencies are ascribed to the "electron sink" properties of the carbonyl group (Allan, Oxford, Robinson and Smith, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 401) on the thiazole cyclisation of *p*-substituted-*s*-diphenylthiocarbamides.

As might be anticipated, *p*-carbethoxy-*s*-diphenylthiocarbamide (I, R=H) gave rise on treatment with bromine under moderately vigorous conditions to ethyl 1-anilinobenzthiazole-4'-carboxylate (II, R=H), whose constitution was established by synthesis from 1-chlorobenzthiazole and ethyl *p*-aminobenzoate. On prolonged bromination in the presence of excess of the halogen, however, nuclear substitution occurred with the production of ethyl 5-bromo-1-anilinobenzthiazole-4'-carboxylate (II, R=Br), whose orientation

follows from its synthesis from 1-chloro-5-bromobenzthiazole and ethyl *p*-aminobenzoate. Curiously enough, although we were able to show the formation of ethyl 5-bromo-1-anilinobenzthiazole-4'-carboxylate in the reaction between *s-p*-carbethoxyphenyl-*p*-bromophenylthiocarbamide (I, R=Br) and bromine, it was not found possible to isolate the base in a condition of purity in this reaction.

s-p-Carbethoxyphenyl-*p*-tolylthiocarbamide (I, R=Me) behaved similarly and yielded ethyl 1-anilino-5-methylbenzthiazole-4'-carboxylate (II, R=Me), identical with that obtained from 1-chloro-5-methylbenzthiazole and ethyl *p*-aminobenzoate.

Difficulties similar to those encountered in the synthesis of ethyl 5-bromo-1-anilinobenzthiazole-4'-carboxylate from *s-p*-carbethoxyphenyl-*p*-bromophenylthiocarbamide were also experienced in connexion with the bromination of *s-p*-carbethoxyphenyl-*p*-chlorophenylthiocarbamide, which gave rise to specimens of ethyl 5-chloro-1-anilinobenzthiazole-4'-carboxylate (II, R=Cl) which could not be completely purified by recrystallisation. The 5-chloro-1-anilinobenzthiazole was, however, obtained in a satisfactory condition of purity from the condensation of ethyl *p*-aminobenzoate with 1:5-dichlorobenzthiazole (III), which was synthesised from 5-chloro-1-aminobenzthiazole by means of the Sandmeyer reaction (*cf.* Hunter and Jones, *loc. cit.*).

It is, therefore, evident that the effect of the carbethoxy group falls well into line with that of the other *meta*-directive substituents previously examined, and particular interest therefore attaches itself to the bromination of *s-p*-carbethoxyphenyl-*p*-nitrophenylthiocarbamide, in which the inhibitory effects of the two *meta*-directing groups

are in opposition: $\text{EtO}\cdot\text{CO}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-\text{NH}\cdot\text{CS}\cdot\text{NH}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-\text{NO}_2^\oplus$.

This thiocarbamide might clearly give rise either to ethyl 5-nitro-1-anilinobenzthiazole-4'-carboxylate (II, $\text{R}=\text{NO}_2$), or to ethyl 4'-nitro-1-anilinobenzthiazole-5-carboxylate (IV), according to the thiazole cyclisation by bromine. The former base was readily synthesised from ethyl *p*-aminobenzoate and 5-nitro-1-chlorobenzthiazole (V), obtained by direct nitration of 1-chlorobenzthiazole (Hofmann, *Ber.*, 1880, 13, 11), which was orientated by its conversion by ammonia into 5-nitro-1-aminobenzthiazole (VI), whose formula has been established by rational synthesis from *p*-nitrophenylthiocarbamide and bromine (Hunter and Jones, *loc. cit.*).

An attempt to synthesise 5-nitro-1-chlorobenzthiazole from *p*-nitrophenylthiocarbimide and phosphorus pentachloride (*cf.* Hofmann, *loc. cit.*) proved unsuccessful, the reaction being accompanied by considerable decomposition and charring.

Bromination of *s-p*-carbethoxyphenyl-*p*-nitrophenylthiocarbamide gave rise to a base isomeric with ethyl 5-nitro-1-anilinobenzthiazole-4'-carboxylate, which is evidently the 4'-nitro derivative (IV).

The effect of the positive pole in the nitro group, therefore, outweighs the "electron sink" capacity of the carbonyl group in *s-p*-carbethoxyphenyl-*p*-nitrophenylthiocarbamide, thiazole cyclisation taking place in this case on the nucleus which carries the *meta*-directive carbethoxyl group.

EXPERIMENTAL.

p-Carbethoxyphenylthiocarbimide (Hunter and Parken, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 359) is best purified by recrystallisation from

petroleum-benzene in which the di-*p*-carbethoxyphenylthiocarbamide, formed as a by-product, is nearly insoluble.

p-Carbethoxy-*s*-diphenylthiocarbamide (I, R=H), prepared by the condensation of the carbethoxyphenylthiocarbimide (2.1 g.) and aniline (1 c.c.) in alcohol or in benzene, crystallised in soft silky flakes, m.p. 129-30°. (Found: S, 11.0. $C_{16}H_{16}O_2N_2S$ requires S, 10.7 per cent).

Ethyl 1-anilinobenzthiazole-4'-carboxylate (II, R=H). (i) *Synthesis from 1-chlorobenzthiazole and ethyl p-aminobenzoate*.—A mixture of 1-chlorobenzthiazole (1 g.) and ethyl *p*-aminobenzoate (1 g.) was gently heated in an open Pyrex-boiling tube over a small luminous flame until a violent reaction occurred and the product was basified with ammonia. On crystallisation from alcohol-ethyl acetate, *ethyl 1-anilinobenzthiazole-4'-carboxylate* was obtained in small crystals, m.p. 182-83°. (Found: S, 10.9. $C_{16}H_{14}O_2N_2S$ requires S, 10.7 per cent).

(ii) *The action of bromine on p-carbethoxy-s-diphenylthiocarbamide*.—The thiocarbamide (0.7 g.) in chloroform (10 c.c.) was treated with bromine (0.8 c.c. in 1 c.c. of chloroform) and the mixture was heated on a steam-bath under reflux for 20 to 25 minutes. The evolution of hydrogen bromide commenced after the first two minutes, heating continued vigorously for a further five minutes, and then gradually abated. On cooling, a red *hydroperbromide* crystallised, which was collected on porous earthenware, dried in a vacuum and added to saturated sulphurous acid (100 c.c.). The suspension was treated with sulphur dioxide and the mixture was kept overnight to ensure complete reduction. On basification with ammonia and recrystallisation from alcohol *ethyl 1-anilinobenzthiazole-4'-carboxylate* was obtained, m.p. 175-76° alone and m.p. 180-83° when mixed with the specimen obtained from 1-chlorobenzthiazole and ethyl *p*-aminobenzoate.

Ethyl 5-bromo-1-anilinobenzthiazole-4'-carboxylate (II, R=Br). (i) *Synthesis from 1-chloro-5-bromobenzthiazole and ethyl p-aminobenzoate*.—1-Chloro-5-bromobenzthiazole which was originally prepared by Dyson, Hunter and Soyka (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 458) in 2% yield from *p*-bromophenylthiocarbimide and phosphorus pentachloride is much more conveniently prepared in quantity from phenylthiocarbamide by means of the following steps: 1-Aminobenzthiazole $\rightarrow$ 5-bromo-1-aminobenzthiazole $\rightarrow$ 1-chloro-5-bromobenzthiazole. The aminobenzthiazole (20 g.) was dissolved in warm chloroform

(130 c. c.) and the solution was cooled in ice and stirred during the addition of bromine (9 c.c. in 10 c. c. of chloroform). The precipitate was collected, dried on porous earthenware in a vacuum, added to saturated sulphurous acid, and sulphur dioxide was passed through the mixture until decolorisation was complete. On basification and recrystallisation from alcohol, 5-bromo-1-aminobenzthiazole was obtained, m. p. $208-10^{\circ}$ which is quite pure enough for the next stage, yield 80-90%. 5-Bromo-1-aminobenzthiazole (25 g.) was treated with 110 c.c. of hydrochloric acid (5-6 %), and the mixture was cooled to 0° and diazotised with sodium nitrite (12.5 g. in 30 c. c. of water). Concentrated hydrochloric acid (200 c.c.) was then added, and the mixture was boiled for 5 minutes and the 1-chloro-5-bromobenzthiazole isolated by distillation in steam. After recrystallisation from alcohol, the chlorothiazole had m. p. $101-102^{\circ}$, yield 7-8 g. Dyson, Hunter, and Soyka recorded the m. p. of 1-chloro-5-bromobenzthiazole, prepared from *p*-bromophenylthiocarbimide and phosphorus pentachloride as 89° . An intimate mixture of 1-chloro-5-bromobenzthiazole (0.55 g.) and ethyl *p*-aminobenzoate (0.5 g.) was heated until condensation took place and the product was basified with ammonia and kept overnight. On recrystallisation from alcohol-ethyl acetate, ethyl 5-bromo-1-anilinobenzthiazole-4'-carboxylate was obtained in small crystals, m. p. $227-28^{\circ}$. (Found: Br, 21.1. $C_{16}H_{13}O_2N_2BrS$ requires Br, 21.2 per cent).

(ii) *Prolonged bromination of p-carbethoxy-s-diphenylthiocarbamide.*—Bromine (1 c.c. in 1 c.c. of chloroform) was added to the carbethoxydiphenylthiocarbamide (0.5 g. in 10 c.c. of the same solvent) and the mixture was heated under reflux on a steam-bath for an hour. The bromo-addition compound was reduced in the usual way and the product recrystallised from methyl alcohol, when ethyl 5-bromo-1-anilinobenzthiazole-4'-carboxylate was obtained which had m.p. 226° , and m.p. $226-28^{\circ}$ when mixed with the specimen obtained from 1-chloro-5-bromobenzthiazole and ethyl *p*-aminobenzoate.

(iii) *The action of bromine on s-p-carbethoxyphenyl-p-bromophenylthiocarbamide.* — *s-p*-Carbethoxyphenyl-*p*-bromophenylthiocarbamide was prepared by mixing solutions of *p*-bromoaniline in benzene (1.7 g. in 8 c.c.) and *p*-carbethoxyphenylthiocarbimide in benzene (2.1 g. in 10 c.c.), and concentrating the resulting solution on a steam-bath. The *thiocarbamide* was washed with petroleum-benzene

and thereafter recrystallised from benzene, from which it separated in glistening plates, m.p. 158-59°, yield 1.8 g. (Found: S, 8.7. $C_{16}H_{15}O_2N_2$ BrS requires S, 8.4 per cent). A solution of the carbethoxyphenylbromophenylthiocarbamide (0.5 g.) in chloroform (10 c. c.) was treated with bromine (1 c. c. in 1 c. c. of chloroform) and the mixture was heated under reflux for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour, cooled, and the bromo-addition compound was dried in a vacuum and reduced with sulphurous acid in the usual way. On recrystallisation from alcohol, ethyl 5-bromo-1-anilinobenzthiazole-4'-carboxylate, was obtained, m.p. 188-90° mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen being 190-92°. Several experiments were carried out in which both the quantity of chloroform used as solvent for bromination, and the time of heating was varied, but in no case was a product of melting point higher than 192-93° isolated. Attempts to raise the melting points of such products by varying the solvents used for recrystallisation proved equally fruitless.

Ethyl 1-anilino-5-methylbenzthiazole-4'-carboxylate (II, R=Me).

(i) 1-Chloro-5-methylbenzthiazole was conveniently prepared from 1-amino-5-methylbenzthiazole by means of the Sandmeyer reaction (. unter and Jones, *loc. cit.*), and crystallised from alcohol in glistening needles, m. p. 49-50°. Ethyl-1-anilino-5-methylbenzthiazole-4'-carboxylate, prepared by condensing equimolecular proportions of 1-chloro-5-methylbenzthiazole and ethyl *p*-aminobenzoate under the usual conditions, separated from alcohol—ethyl acetate in small crystals, m. p. 206-207°. (Found: S, 10.6. $C_{17}H_{16}O_2N_2S$ requires S, 10.3 per cent).

(ii) *The action of bromine on p-carbethoxyphenyl-p-tolylthiocarbamide.*—*p*-Carbethoxyphenyl-*p*-tolylthiocarbamide was prepared by the condensation of equimolecular proportions of *p*-carbethoxyphenylthiocarbamide and *p*-toluidine in benzene solution, washed with petroleum-benzene and recrystallised from boiling benzene. It formed glistening plates, m. p. 160-61°. (Found: S, 10.2. $C_{17}H_{18}O_2N_2S$ requires S, 10.2 per cent). The carbethoxyphenyltolylthiocarbamide (0.5 g.) in chloroform (10 c.c.) was treated with bromine (0.6 c.c. in 1 c.c. of chloroform) and the mixture was heated under reflux for 15 minutes. The evolution of hydrogen bromide which was copious after the first two minutes' heating abated after 10 minutes. The solution was cooled in ice and the red crystalline hydroperbromide was dried in a vacuum and reduced in the usual way by sulphurous acid and sulphur dioxide. On basification and recrystallisation from

alcohol-ethyl acetate, ethyl 1-anilino-5-methylbenzthiazole-4'-carboxylate was obtained which had m.p. 206°, and m.p. 206-207° when mixed with the specimen prepared from 1-chloro-5-methylbenzthiazole and ethyl *p*-aminobenzoate.

Ethyl 5-chloro-1-anilinobenzthiazole-4'-carboxylate (II, R = Cl).

(i) *Synthesis from 1:5 dichlorobenzthiazole and ethyl p-aminobenzoate.* 1:5—*Dichlorobenzthiazole*.—6.2 G. of 5-chloro-1-aminobenzthiazole (Dyson, Hunter and Morris, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 1186) were treated with hydrochloric acid as in the case of the 5-bromo derivative, and diazotised with sodium nitrite (8.1 g.) at 0° and the diazonium salt was treated with concentrated hydrochloric acid and the mixture was boiled. The *dichlorobenzthiazole*, isolated by steam distillation, crystallised from alcohol in needles, m.p. 101°, yield 2.8 g. (Found: Cl, 35.1. $C_7H_5NCl_2S$ requires Cl, 34.8 per cent). *Ethyl 5-chloro-1-anilinobenzthiazole-4'-carboxylate*, prepared from the condensation of an equimolecular mixture of 1:5-dichlorobenzthiazole and ethyl *p*-aminobenzoate had m.p. 226°. (Found: Cl, 10.5. $C_{16}H_{13}O_2N_2ClS$ requires Cl, 10.7 per cent).

(ii) *The action of bromine on s-p-carbethoxyphenyl-p-chlorophenylthiocarbamide.* *s-p-Carbethoxyphenyl-p-chlorophenylthiocarbamide*, prepared by condensation of *p*-carbethoxyphenylthiocarbimide (2.1 g.) and *p*-chloroaniline (1.2 g.) in benzene, separated from a comparatively large volume of benzene in plates, m.p. 159-60°, yield 1.8 g. (Found: S, 9.7. $C_{16}H_{15}O_2N_2ClS$ requires S, 9.6 per cent). The carbethoxyphenylchlorophenylthiocarbamide (0.5 g.) in chloroform (10 c.c.) was treated with bromine (1 c.c. in 1 c.c. of chloroform) and the mixture was heated under reflux for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. The hydroperbromide was dried in a vacuum and reduced with sulphurous acid and sulphur dioxide in the usual way. On basification and recrystallisation from alcohol, ethyl 5-chloro-1-anilinobenzthiazole-4'-carboxylate was obtained which had m.p. 178° and m.p. 179-201° when mixed with the specimen prepared from the dichlorobenzthiazole and ethyl *p*-aminobenzoate. In a similar experiment in which the carbethoxyphenylchlorophenylthiocarbamide (0.45 g.) in chloroform (10 c.c.) was treated with bromine (0.9 c.c. in 1 c.c. of chloroform), and heating under reflux was continued for 43 to 45 minutes, a bromo-addition compound was obtained which on reduction and recrystallisation of the resulting anilinobenzthiazole gave a crop of crystals which had m.p. 163° and m.p. 190-201° when mixed with a genuine specimen. All attempts to purify this product by further fractional crystallisation, however, proved unsuccessful.

Synthesis of ethyl 5-nitro-1-anilinobenzthiazole-4'-carboxylate (II, R=NO₂). (i) *Nitration of 1-chlorobenzthiazole and the orientation of 5-nitro-1-chlorobenzthiazole by its conversion into 5-nitro-1-aminobenzthiazole.*—Chlorobenzthiazole (prepared by the Sandmeyer method from 1-aminobenzthiazole) was gradually added drop by drop with stirring to fuming nitric acid (*d* 1.5, 10 vols.) cooled in a freezing mixture. The solution was kept for a short time and then poured into a large volume of water and the precipitated nitrochlorobenzthiazole was collected and recrystallised from ethyl acetate, from which it separated in yellow needles, m.p. 190° (*cf.* Hofmann, *loc. cit.*). The nitrochlorobenzthiazole (0.2 g.) was heated with ammonia (*d* 0.880, 2.5 c.c.) in a sealed tube at 150-160° for 6 to 7 hours and the product was collected and recrystallised from alcohol, when 5-nitro-1-aminobenzthiazole was obtained which had m.p. 242-43° alone and when mixed with an authentic specimen prepared in an earlier investigation (Hunter and Jones, *loc. cit.*). The identity was further confirmed by conversion of the 5-nitro-1-aminobenzthiazole into its pale yellow acetyl derivative by means of acetic anhydride, which had m.p. 292° alone and when mixed with an authentic specimen. (ii) *Synthesis of ethyl 5-nitro-1-anilinobenzthiazole-4'-carboxylate from 5-nitro-1-chlorobenzthiazole and ethyl p-aminobenzoate.*—A mixture of the nitrochlorobenzthiazole (1 mol.) and ethyl *p*-aminobenzoate (1 mol.) was gently heated in a boiling tube over a naked flame until a violent reaction took place. The product was treated with dilute ammonia and recrystallised from alcohol, when ethyl 5-nitro-1-anilinobenzthiazole-4'-carboxylate was obtained in small yellow plates, m.p. 242-43°. (Found: S, 9.5. C₁₇H₁₃O₄N₃S requires S, 9.2 per cent).

The action of bromine on s-p-carbethoxyphenyl-p-nitrophenylthiocarbamide, and the isolation of ethyl 4'-nitro-1-anilinobenzthiazole-5-carboxylate. *s-p-Carbethoxyphenyl-p-nitrophenylthiocarbamide.*—A solution of *p*-nitroaniline (1.7 g.) in alcohol (10 c.c.) was added to a solution of *p*-carbethoxyphenylthiocarbimide in the same solvent (2 g. in 10 c.c.) and the mixture was concentrated on a steam-bath. On recrystallisation from alcohol, the carbethoxyphenylnitrophenylthiocarbamide was obtained in orange crystals, m.p. 154-55°, yield, 1.2 g. (Found: S, 8.9. C₁₇H₁₅O₄N₃S requires S, 9.2 per cent). In a similar experiment in which benzene was used as a medium of condensation in place of alcohol, this yield was raised to 1.8 g.

The nitrophenylthiocarbamide (0.5 g.) in chloroform (12 c.c.) was treated with bromine (1 c.c. in 1 c.c. of the same solvent) and the

mi xture was heated on a steam-bath under reflux for 55 minutes. The bromo-addition compound was dried in a vacuum and reduced by sulphurous acid. On basification with ammonia (d 0.880) and recrystallisation from alcohol, ethyl 4'-nitro-1-anilinobenzthiazole-4'-carboxylate was obtained in yellow crystals of a slightly deeper shade of colour than the isomeric ethyl 5-nitro-1-anilinobenzthiazole-4'-carboxylate, m.p. 241-43°. (Found: S, 9.5. $C_{17}H_{13}O_4N_3S$ requires S, 9.2 per cent). The appearance of the two nitroanilinobenzthiazoles was quite distinct and a mixture of the two bases melted at 218°.

The interaction of p-nitrophenylthiocarbimide and phosphorus pentachloride.—An intimate mixture (3 g.) of *p*-nitrophenylthiocarbimide (Dyson and George, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 128, 1702) and phosphorus pentachloride (3.5 g.) was heated in a sealed tube at 150-160° for 6 hours. The dark brown oily liquid was gradually added to water to decompose phosphorus halides and the mixture was extracted with chloroform. After removal of the chloroform on a steam-bath and recrystallisation from alcohol, a yellow-brown crystalline substance was obtained, m.p. 180°. This product, however, did not possess any of the properties of 5-nitro-1-chlorobenzthiazole and admixture with a specimen of the nitro derivative obtained from 1-chlorobenzthiazole caused a depression in melting point of 40 to 50°.

